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Challenging Amatonormativity

Re-introducing the hidden world of Neuroscience

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**InclusiSex Studies Initiative, Pillow Talk With Nixi, San Francisco,
CA**

AASECT 2024 Conference

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Elizabeth Baker

Amatonormativity is the set of societal assumptions that everyone prospers with an exclusive romantic relationship, heavily guarded by heteronormative standards and solely existing within a reproductive narrative.

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THE CON TENT

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the complex dynamics that affect gender identity formation and the nuanced understanding of relational dynamics, conceptualized as a product of various intersecting factors such as genetics, hormones, anatomy, environment, and social construction.

It highlights chromosomal transitions that challenge the traditional binary models of gender, emphasizing the need for an inclusive approach.

Furthermore, neurobiology sheds light on the role of the brain in the formation of sexual perception and gender identity. Contrary to held biases, brain structures such as the bed nucleus stria terminalis (BNST) and the sexually dimorphic nucleus of the preoptic area (SDN-POA) are known to be influenced not only by hormonal exposures but also by socio-sexual experiences. These findings highlight the potential for gender-specific fluid characteristics in development.

Furthermore, neurotransmitters such as vasopressin and dopamine play a crucial role in the regulation of relational dynamics and pair-bonding. The function of the human brain is to create behavior in a perceived world created by the brain.

Bringing together evidence from genetics, neuroscience, and behavioral studies, this research challenges traditional binary models and develops a comprehensive understanding of sex and gender. It also questions the amatonormative biases held concerning relational dynamics, providing us with a fluid understanding of human socio-sexual interactions.

Keywords: social development, sex binary, gender identity, non-monogamy

Sex & Gender

To challenge Amatonormativity is to an established understanding of sexuality, gender identity, lifestyle choices and reproductive choices. Scientists have always had its flagbearers the binary system to drive their research. However, sex is non-binary. People cannot be characterized as Male or Female, as there exist various chromosomal combinations: 46 XX, 46 XY, 45X, 47XXY, 47XYY, 47XXX, 48XXXX, 48XXXY, 48XXYY, 49XXXXX, 49XXXXY.

It has long been understood that gender is also a social construct. Gender cannot be defined by chromosomes (X and Y) for it is a highly complex social construct that develops from interactions of genes, chromosomes, hormones, internal sex organs and external secondary sexual characteristics with the environment: the roles individuals are conditioned to play, the roles they'd like to play, how they are socialized, stereotypes and sexism they have been exposed to, and even religion and faith based systems they are surrounded by (Appendix A1, A2).

To solely assume an identity for an individual based on their external sex organs such as a penis and or a vulva, completely disregards 2% of the population that are born as intersex, with ambiguous genitalia at birth, Micropenis, clitoromegaly (an enlarged clitoris), partial labial fusion, undescended testes (which may turn out to be ovaries) in boys or even labial or inguinal (groin) masses (which may turn out to be testes) in girls, which often get misinterpreted and assumed so that one can be socialized into the narrative of the Sex Binary.

Let's consider the Guevedoces case from Dominican Republic, where it was reported that children bearing the chromosomal composition of 46XY, were brought up as women due to a delay in the descent of testes (12 years of age) ((Marks L.S. 2004); Fig. 1). The resultant cause was a congenital deficiency of 5α -reductase

Fig. 1. A Guevedoces Case Study done in Dominican Republic, indicating the arrested development of male-specific sexual characteristics due to a congenital deficiency of 5α -reductase. (Marks LS, et al., 2016).

Sexual Partner Preference

A sexual partner preference within the scientific community has long been gauged under the lens of normalcy and its occurrence within the phallogenic scale of behaviors. The normal, as defined by the phallogenic society as heterosexual behaviors portrayed by cis-men.

“A woman who makes her emotional and intimate life with another woman is seen as having fallen from the path of true feminine development, expressing masculine and not feminine identification and desires”, remarked psychoanalysts, Maggie Magee and Diana Miller (Magee, M., & Miller, D. C., 1997).

This **Amatonormative** society would have us believe that we should exist solely in a heteronormative fashion. However, our brain disagrees, as recorded in the Sexually Dimorphic Nucleus of the Preoptic Area (SDN-POA). In humans, its also called the Interstitial Nucleus of the Anterior Hypothalamus (INAH- 3) Cluster. Sexual Differences in the brain develop due to varying degrees of Testosterone exposure during development, as indicated in male rats having a larger Medial Preoptic Area (mPOA) than the females.

Soon, researchers proved that the size of the SDN-POA infers male-typical (mounting)/female-typical (lordosis) sexual behaviors. When injected with testosterone, females would mount other females and in castrated males (absence of testosterone), a display of lordosis in the presence of another male was observed.

In humans, a het. v. hom. study revealed a smaller INAH-3 cluster in hom-men when compared to het-men. It is also indicative of hom. women having a larger INAH-3 cluster when compared to Het. women.

Transsexual research provided a further conclusive evidence of trans-men having a similar INAH-3 cluster as cis-men, and trans women having a similar size to cis-women ((LeVay, 1991); Fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Volumes of 4 nuclei (INAH 1-4) studied in females (F); heterosexual males (M); homosexual males (HM) (LeVay, 1991)

Gender Identity

Gender Identity has been brought several times to the forefront, its underlying genetic or neural correlates often being gauged upon. The characterization of the identity is often rooted in binary codes, suggesting for the usage of terms such as “Male specific behaviors” or “Female specific behaviors” to define mounting and lordosis, respectively.

Post-mortem studies involving transsexual people indicate a gender specific difference in the size of the Bed Nucleus Stria Terminalis (BNST). A study had recorded the similarity between trans-women and cis-women’s BNST, rendering it smaller than their counterparts, trans-men ((Zhou et al., 1995); Fig. 3 & 4). They even tried to find a link between homosexuality and gender identity by comparing the results with homosexual men. To note here, the study uses a gender identity as “male” as the norm, all the while countering it with other identities and sexual orientations.

In 2021, a genomic study documented an evolutionary maintained allele as a factor for same-sex sexual behavior, when in fact the allele was previously documented as a personality trait for “openness”, which could have mediated same-sex sexual behaviors.

Fig. 3. Neural somatostatin cells of the BNST in (A) heterosexual man; (B) heterosexual woman; (C) homosexual man; (D) male to female transsexual (Zhou et al., 1995)

Fig. 4. BNSTc innervated with VIP fibers in heterosexual males (M), homosexual males (HM), heterosexual females (F) and male to female transsexuals (TM) (Zhou et al., 1995)

Stress & Neurodevelopment

Consider the hypotheses of certain brain areas contributing to certain behavioral profiles. To run a simulation to prove the correlation, one has to make some assumptions regarding certain environmental or nurturing factors, rendering this theory inconclusive to define a populous in the real world, experiencing a constantly evolving and stressful environment.

To argue for that, if one were to take up the argument of BNST serving as a marker for gender identity, then one makes a large and gross assumption that all individuals participating in this study have always experienced the same factors contributing to their development. This begs the introduction of stress and its impacts on brain development.

The underlying mechanism such as stress plays a major role in pruning of neuronal connections in childhood. In a study comprising of transgender and cisgender children involved in executing a task, the former showed lower basal cortisol levels, indicative of chronic stress. Their results were also indicative of baseline galvanic skin resistance, suggesting to a higher arousal and sympathetic activity before the introduction of stressors ((Wallien et al., 2007); Fig.5).

The somatostatin cells of the BNST are heavily stress dependent. In a highly stressed individual, at baseline, the microcircuit consisting of BNST somatostatin cells function in the same manner a healthy individual's cells under stress. Studies indicate that chronic stress reduces the somatostatin cell count ((Fee et al., 2017); Fig.6).

Identifying one's gender and transition can be highly stressful, which can lead to apoptosis of the cells of concern in the BNST, which impacts the data.

Fig. 5. Negative feelings in children with GID and matched control children. GID = gender identity disorder; MC = matched controls (Wallien et al., 2007)

Fig. 6. Neural somatostatin cells in a healthy and pathological circuit, indicating that in the latter, at baseline, the cells function as if they are enduring a stressful stimuli (Fee et al., 2017)

Relational Lifestyles

Connectionist models, arguing for function of behavior emerging from strengthened neural circuits, are often used to study relational lifestyles.

From a neurotransmitter standpoint, it has long been established that Arginine Vasopressin (AVP), Oxytocin (OT) and Dopamine (D) play a major role in social affiliation, mating, pair bonding, partner preference, mate guarding and pair-bond maintenance.

However, a degreed variance is visible across species, regional brain sites, corresponding neurotransmitter and degree of behavior thus exhibited. For example, while Dopamine D2 receptors in the Nucleus Accumbens (NAcc) are important for pair-bond formation, Dopamine D1 receptors in the NAcc are involved in maintaining pair-bonds. This however is applicable only to prairie voles. As we move to mandarin voles, D1 receptors lose their importance. With titi monkeys, AVP and D1 receptors in the Lateral Septum (LS) play a role, while in a common marmoset, both are dysregulated and OT plays a role ((López-Gutiérrez MF et al., 2022); Appendix B).

With such a degreed variance, it is close to impossible to predict underlying factors with humans as the two interconnected circuits, the social behavioral network and the mesolimbic reward system, have high plasticity, constantly adapting to the evolving social environment. It is however, hypothesized that the social decision-making network (SDMN), plays a major role in regulating pair-bonding behavior (Newman, 1999; O'Connell and Hofmann, 2011).

Characterizing the role played by AVP and OT in humans draws a blank as these neurotransmitters don't cross the blood brain barrier, making it difficult to obtain real-time data.

To address the evolutionary advantage hypothesis, there isn't any data to suggest that pair-bonding was in-fact an evolutionary advantage for an AFAB person. In fact there exists several hypotheses that contest the aforementioned one's existence: for example, "Higher the female vocalization, higher the promiscuity within female bonding", "Kamikaze sperm theory suggesting that 40% of the sperm exist to plug the vaginal canal to prevent the entry of another's sperms" and "Semen Displacement Theory suggesting that the mushroom head of the penis exists to scoop out another person's semen and replace it with your own".

All of these theories are heavily dependent on the existence of women on a reproductive scale: their pair-bonding nature and pleasure considered secondary to their "biological function".

Reproduction

In an amatonormative society, individuals exist within a reproductive scale, their partnered existence solely utilized towards a single goal, often disregarding their own needs, wants and desires.

The field of reproductive medicine has drastically changed ever since assisted reproductive techniques (ARTs) were developed. One such technique called In-Vitro Gametogenesis (IVG) has been making headlines.

IVG calls for stem cells being utilized from two individuals (irrespective of their gender and sex assigned at birth) to develop an egg and a sperm, so as to provide genetically similar children to parents of any sexual orientation and gender identity (Hayashi, K. et al, 2012).

Another ART namely, Parthenogenesis has had a proven natural existence in many species of birds and fish. It is now being utilized to provide a 2X embryo to a vulva bearer, without the need for a sperm to fertilize the egg (Awad Hegazy, A. et al., 2023).

Fig. 7. primordial germ cell-like cells (PGCLC)-derived offspring (Hayashi, K. et al, 2012)

Fig. 8. Proposed automixis mechanism of PG and development of OT.s (Awad Hegazy, A. et al., 2023)

Discussion

While arguments regarding Sexual and Gender Identity are rooted in regional brain volume studies, arguments defining relational lifestyle choices takes the approach of connectionist models.

The regional brain volume studies accounted for so far, are 11 in numbers, with fewer than 30 participants, with limited representation across demographics, little to no congruence with sex, gender identity and assigned brain volumes, and the findings, show no repetitions in follow-up studies.

This shift in scientific approach advocates for inclusivity by focusing on networks that are strengthened over time as opposed to a conventional sex binary outlook toward behaviors.

Although, there exists an advancement in the approach towards imaging brain networks that underlie behaviors, there still exists a male-typical and a female-typical behavior profile which sets the norm in data collection, adding to the variability in data collection. Irrespective of the advancement in imaging techniques, scientists still rely on a binary foundation making it harder to successfully determine the underlying neural mechanisms.

There exists a biological reductionism, a need to find an underlying pattern for behaviors, such as genes or neural correlates to behaviors, disregarding factors that may influence the strengthening of certain behaviors from a survival standpoint. Complex social and cultural identities, and their underlying mechanisms can never be generalized across the populous. The function of the nervous system is to create behavior in a perceived world created by the brain.

Species variation in neuroendocrine involvement in depicting monogamous/pair-bonded behavior makes it harder to characterize the underlying circuitry for the development of aforementioned behavioral profiles.

Moreover, advancements in reproductive medicine have paved a new pathway that differs from the binary dogma of fertilization, thus providing same-sex parents an avenue to birth genetically similar offsprings. This also provides single parents an advantage to birth children without the need for a partnered dynamic in reproductive stages, debunking the need for an amatonormative existence.

References

- Awad Hegazy, A., Ibraheem Al-Qtaitat, A., & Awad Hegazy, R. (2023). A new hypothesis may explain human parthenogenesis and ovarian teratoma: A review study. *International journal of reproductive biomedicine*, 21(4), 277–284. <https://doi.org/10.18502/ijrm.v21i4.13267>
- Baker, R.R., Bellis, M.A. (2006). “Kamikaze” sperm in mammals? (1988). In: Shackelford, T.K., Pound, N. (eds) *Sperm Competition in Humans*. Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-28039-4_5
- Brake, E. (2012). *Minimizing marriage: Marriage, morality, and the law*. Oxford University Press.
- Carrillo, B., Gómez-Gil, E., Rametti, G., Junque, C., Gomez, A., Karadi, K., Segovia, S., and Chung WC, De Vries GJ, Swaab DF. Sexual differentiation of the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis in humans may extend into adulthood. *J Neurosci*. 2002 Feb 1;22(3):1027–33. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.22-03-01027.2002. PMID: 11826131; PMCID: PMC6758506.
- DF Swaab (2004) Sexual differentiation of the human brain: relevance for gender identity, transsexualism and sexual orientation, *Gynecological Endocrinology*, 19:6, 301–312, DOI: [10.1080/09513590400018231](https://doi.org/10.1080/09513590400018231)
- Fee, C., Banasr, M., & Sibille, E. (2017). Somatostatin-Positive Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid Interneuron Deficits in Depression: Cortical Microcircuit and Therapeutic Perspectives. *Biological psychiatry*, 82(8), 549–559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2017.05.024>
- Garcia-Falgueras A, Swaab DF. A sex difference in the hypothalamic uncinate nucleus: relationship to gender identity. *Brain*. 2008 Dec;131(Pt 12):3132–46. doi: 10.1093/brain/awn276. Epub 2008 Nov 2. PMID: 18980961.
- Gorski RA, Gordon JH, Shryne JE, Southam AM (1978) Evidence for a morphological sex difference within the medial preoptic area of the rat brain. *Brain Res* 148:333–346.
- Guillamon, A. (2010). Cortical activation during mental rotation in male-to-female and female-to-male transsexuals under hormonal treatment. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* 35, 1213–1222.
- Harcourt, A. H., Harvey, P. H., Larson, S. G., and Short, R. V. (1981). Testis weight, body weight and breeding system in primates. *Nature*, 293:55. doi: 10.1038/293055a0
- Hayashi, K., Ogushi, S., Kurimoto, K., Shimamoto, S., Ohta, H., & Saitou, M. (2012). Offspring from Oocytes Derived from in Vitro Primordial Germ Cell-like Cells in Mice. *Science*, 338(6109), 971–975. doi:10.1126/science.1226889
- Hofman MA, Swaab DF. The sexually dimorphic nucleus of the preoptic area in the human brain: a comparative morphometric study. *J Anat*. 1989 Jun;164:55–72. PMID: 2606795; PMCID: PMC1256598.
- Hostetler CM, Hinde K, Maninger N, Mendoza SP, Mason WA, Rowland DJ, Wang GB, Kukis D, Cherry SR, Bales KL. Effects of pair bonding on dopamine D1 receptors in monogamous male titi monkeys (*Callicebus cupreus*). *Am J Primatol*. 2017 Mar;79(3):1–9. doi: 10.1002/ajp.22612. Epub 2016 Oct 18. PMID: 27757971; PMCID: PMC5474115.
- Houtsmuller EJ, Brand T, de Jonge FH, Joosten RN, van de Poll NE, Slob AK. SDN-POA volume, sexual behavior, and partner preference of male rats affected by perinatal treatment with ATD. *Physiol Behav*. 1994 Sep;56(3):535–41. doi: 10.1016/0031-9384(94)90298-4. PMID: 7972405.
- Kiyar, Meltem, Collet, Sarah, T’Sjoen, Guy and Mueller, Sven C.. "Neuroscience in transgender people: an update" *Neuroforum*, vol. 26, no. 2, 2020, pp. 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.1515/nf-2020-0007>
- LeVay, Simon. A Difference in Hypothalamic Structure Between Heterosexual and Homosexual Men. *Science*. August 30, 1991, Vol. 253, No. 5023, 1034–1037.

References

- LeVay, S. (1996). *Queer science: The use and abuse of research into homosexuality*. The MIT Press.
- López-Gutiérrez, M. F., Mejía-Chávez, S., Alcauter, S., & Portillo, W. (2022). The neural circuits of monogamous behavior. *Frontiers in neural circuits*, 16, 978344. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncir.2022.978344>
- Luo, Y., & Yu, Y. (2022). Research Advances in Gametogenesis and Embryogenesis Using Pluripotent Stem Cells. *Frontiers in cell and developmental biology*, 9, 801468. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2021.801468>
- Magee, M., & Miller, D. C. (1997). *Lesbian lives: Psychoanalytic narratives old and new*. Analytic Press.
- Marks L. S. (2004). 5alpha-reductase: history and clinical importance. *Reviews in urology*, 6 Suppl 9(Suppl 9), S11–S21.
- Maslin, M., & Leakey, R. E. (2017). *The Cradle of Humanity: How the Changing Landscape of Africa Made Us So Smart*: Oxford University Press.
- Newman S. W. (1999). The medial extended amygdala in male reproductive behavior. A node in the mammalian social behavior network. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 877, 242–257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1999.tb09271.x>
- O'Connell, L. A., & Hofmann, H. A. (2011). The vertebrate mesolimbic reward system and social behavior network: a comparative synthesis. *The Journal of Comparative Neurology*, 519(18), 3599–3639. doi:10.1002/cne.22735
- Parker Geoff A. 2020. Conceptual developments in sperm competition: a very brief synopsis. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 375:2020006120200061
- Pierce, M. L., French, J. A., & Murray, T. F. (2020). Comparison of the pharmacologic profiles of arginine vasopressin and oxytocin analogs at marmoset, titi monkey, macaque, and human oxytocin receptors. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie*, 125, 109832. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2020.109832>
- Ristori J, Cocchetti C, Romani A, Mazzoli F, Vignozzi L, Maggi M, Fisher AD. Brain Sex Differences Related to Gender Identity Development: Genes or Hormones? *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020 Mar 19;21(6):2123. doi: 10.3390/ijms21062123. PMID: 32204531; PMCID: PMC7139786.
- Simmons LW, Fitzpatrick JL. Sperm wars and the evolution of male fertility. *Reproduction*. 2012 Nov;144(5):519–34. doi: 10.1530/REP-12-0285. Epub 2012 Sep 14. PMID: 22984191
- Simmons, L. W., Firman, R. C., and Rhodes, G. (2004). Human sperm competition: Testis size, sperm production and rates of extrapair copulations. *Anim. Behav.* 68, 297–302. doi: 10.1016/j.anbehav.2003.11.013
- Wallien, M. S., & Cohen-Kettenis, P. T. (2008). Psychosexual outcome of gender-dysphoric children. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 47(12), 1413–1423. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CHI.0b013e31818956b9>
- Zhou, J., Hofman, M., Gooren, L.J., and Swaab, D.F. (1995). A sex difference in the human brain and its relation to transsexuality. *Nature* 378, 68–70.
- Zietsch, B. P., Sidari, M. J., Abdellaoui, A., Maier, R., Långström, N., Guo, S., ... Verweij, K. J. H. (2021). Genomic evidence consistent with antagonistic pleiotropy may help explain the evolutionary maintenance of same-sex sexual behaviour in humans. *Nature Human Behaviour*. doi:10.1038/s41562-021-01168-8

Appendix A.1

Table 1: *Psychological Outcomes of Children Raised as Males with Unusual Genitalia*

DEVELOPMENTAL PATTERN (SAMPLE SIZE)	CHANGE IN ASSIGNED SEX	MEDICAL INTERVENTION	METHODS OF ASSESSMENT	OUTCOME	COMMENTS
XX intersex (1)	None; raised as male	Age 11: removal of 1 ovary; age 24: ovarian biopsy	Physical and hormonal only	A married male with a satisfactory sex life	Never told about his actual physical condition
Small penis, bifid scrotum, urinate at base of phallus; at puberty breast growth and identification of uterus, oviducts, and ovaries	Raised as male; reassigned female as teenager	Vaginal reconstruction at age 17; no clitoral surgery	Physical, hormonal, psychiatric interviews, and MMPI, Rorschach test	Married at age 20 and hoping to have child	As a child liked being a boy; received considerable sex ed from parents; mother encouraged her to be secret about genitals because of anatomical difference
Sexual precocity in genetic, gonadal, and hormonal male (1)	None; raised as male	Extensive family counseling	IQ; standard psychological tests; interviews	"Thoroughly adequate psychological adjustment" (p. 15)	Healthy family life
XX intersex; small hypospadiac phallus; fused, empty labioscrotum (1)	None; raised as male	As teenager, breasts and female internal organs removed; hormone treatments; at age 25 plastic surgery on penis	Extensive interviews	Married male; "to the world at large . . . he passed as an ordinary male college graduate—one of the more stable and well-adjusted" (p. 317)	Only case study in a paper that summarizes a large number of studies but gives few specific details
CAH; small phallus with urethra running through it (1)	None; raised as male; hematuria at age 18 warranted medical workup	At age 18, removal of uterus and ovaries; hormonal treatment	Clinical report	"Attending college, majoring in music, and was interested in sports"; had sexual contacts with women (p. 157)	"At age 10 the patient noticed that his external genitalia were smaller than those of other boys his age, and, from that time on, took care not to expose himself before his schoolmates" (p. 156)
CAH; penile urethra; phallus 5 cm long at age 21 (1)	None; raised as male; cyclic urethral bleeding	None	Physical only	A married male	No data given on psychological status
CAH; pubic and axillary hair since age 5; menstruation at age 26; micropenis; penile urethra (1)	None; at age 35 expressed wish to be a woman	Adrenal surgery, which resulted in death of patient	Physical and casual observation	Normal intelligence; served in Army during WWII	During adolescence, attracted to male companions
Same physical development (1) (Younger brother of previous case)	None	Hormone treatment starting at age 25 (refused surgery due to death of brother)	Physical and casual observation	Married at age 22; had sexual intercourse regularly	Began menstruation at 22
CAH with microphallus (2)	None; raised as males	Ovaries, uterus removed at ages 12 and 31, respectively	Psychological, via interview	Both married; one with child via donor insemination; rate sex lives as good	Adapted to sexual activity other than vaginal intercourse
Intersex with small penis and developed breasts (1)	One; raised as male	At 15 yrs. surgical removal of ovary and uterus	None	Married to a woman, sought infertility counseling	
Intersex; enlarged clitoris, menstruation; good breast development, no beard, pubic, or axillary hair (1)	None; raised as male	At age 20: removed ovary and uterus but left remaining ovo-testis	Physical and brief observation	Married as a male; worked as a farmer	"Comparatively quiet . . . preferred to work alone . . . had some inferiority complex" (p. 148)
Intersex raised as male (1)	None	Ovo-testis removed at age 29	Case report of interviews	Aware of genital abnormality since age 8; managed to hide it and was active in male sports such as football; worked in masculine occupations; married at age 26 to a genetic and social female	Breast development at age 15 led him to abandon competitive swimming and football
Abnormal genitalia, enlarged breasts, periodic hematuria (1)	None; raised as male	Surgery at age 21 to remove uterus and ovary	Conversations with patient	Patient behaved, worked as a male; had female sexual partners	Wanted to make him female; patient refused, preferring sex of rearing
Ambiguous genitalia, breasts (1)	None; raised as male	At age 15–16: mastoplasty, 3-stage repair of hypospadias, hysterectomy	Conversations with patient	Participated in sports with other boys; "social adaptation adequate throughout childhood" (p. 663)	
Intersex raised as male (1)	None	As a young man: hysterectomy to stop menstruation and breast reduction	Case report	Patient "totally pleased" (p. 1151), but he had to sit down to urinate	Patient managed to conceal from his family his need to sit down to urinate
Various causes: hormonal and secondary body morphology contradicted assigned sex (27)*	None; 4 raised as males; 23 raised as females	Uncertain	Psychological and physical	"4 ambivalent with respect to gender role" (p. 256)	All ambivalent cases reared as girls
Intersex: XX, XY mosaic; breasts and hematuria; unusual genitalia noted at birth (1)	None; raised as male	Diagnosis at age 14 included uterus and fallopian tubes, which were removed	Case report focused on chromosome composition	Psychological examiners recommended against sex change	No details of life outcome

Appendix A.2

Table 2: *Psychological Outcomes of Children Raised as Females with Unusual Genitalia*

DEVELOPMENTAL PATTERN (SAMPLE SIZE)	CHANGE IN ASSIGNED SEX	MEDICAL INTERVENTION	METHODS OF ASSESSMENT	OUTCOME	COMMENTS
Raised as female with a penislike clitoris; menstruated at 13 (1)	None	Surgery in adulthood; clitoral amputation	Psychological, hormonal	States that patient was satisfied	Patient was primarily attracted to women but had a female gender identity; psychiatrist wanted to surgically turn her into a man (to prevent homosexuality?), but she refused
Sexual precocity in genetic, gonadal, and hormonal female (3)	None; raised as female	Extensive family counseling	IQ and standard psychological tests and interviews	2/3 well adjusted; 1 predicted to become psychotic	Unadjusted individual has psychotic father/poorly adjusted family
XY intersex; enlarged clitoris (2–3 cm); bifid scrotum; urinates through vagina (2 “sisters”)	None; raised as female	None; examined at time of marriage because of urinary oddity	Physical, hormonal	Apparently healthy females who married	Both aware of physique at age 10 because of how they urinated. No mention of discomfort with large clitoris
XY intersex; small penis and vagina (1)	None; raised as female	As a married adult, penis removed and vagina dilated	None	Happily married but infertile	
XY intersex; malformed external genitalia; no breast development (1)	None; raised as female	At age 21 testes removed, vagina enlarged, estrogen treated	Unknown	“Quite well adjusted in her role as a woman” (p. 43)	
Testicular failure; ambiguous but feminized genitalia (3)	Sex change from female to male at ages 20–33		Conversations with physician	2: no information; 1: “patient most satisfied” (p. 1,214)	Calls for a “somewhat less rigid attitude” about when to do surgery (p. 1,216)
Normal male with severe perineal hypospadias, raised as female (1)	Sex reassigned at 14	Surgery to correct hypospadias	Psychological tests and interviews	Successful adjustment following a period of several months	“The Johns Hopkins team . . . [has] not provided convincing evidence” for view that early sex change is imperative (p. 1,217)
CAH females (7)	None; raised as female	None	Psychological and interviews	2 are married; “were entirely feminine in their outlook and ways” (p. 200)	
Various causes: hormonal and secondary body morphology contradicted assigned sex (27)*	None; 4 raised as males, 23 as females	Uncertain	Psychological and physical	“4 ambivalent with respect to gender role” (p. 256)	All ambivalent cases reared as girls
Intersex with penis, bifid scrotum, testes, and ovaries (2)	None; raised as female	At age 26 and 24, surgery to reshape genitalia	Conversations with physicians; physical	Both married as women; “apparently normal girls” (p. 280)	One had no vaginal opening; husband had “intercourse” using space between perineum and legs; the other had no orgasms; both experienced postsurgical loss of libido
Penis-sized clitoris (1)	None; raised as female	At age 17, penile extirpation and vaginal dilation	None	Patient felt herself to be female	“She was, with some difficulty, persuaded to submit to surgical treatment” (p. 79)
Hypospadias; raised as female (1)	Changed from female to male at age 13	Several surgeries at patient’s request to repair hypospadias	Extensive firsthand account of how he coped with the change	Married with 2 adopted children	Wishes he could have intercourse and biological children, but resigned; “I have a full and for the most part happy life” (p. 1,256)
Hypospadias; raised as female (1)	Changed from female to male at age 13	Surgical repair of hypospadias and exposure of hooded penis	Anecdotal	Successful marriage	Patient anxious to make the change, “had his own ideas . . . even to selection of a name and a decidedly masculine program of activities” (p. 490)
Intersex; raised as female (1)	None	Surgery at 18 to open vagina	Case report	Identified as male at birth but mother raised as female; oriented toward males and wished to marry	Early in her life the patient was told by her mother that “she was different from other boys and girls and that she should not let others see her genitalia” (p. 431)
Intersex, raised as male (1)	None	Repair of hypospadias at age 29	Case report	Married to genetic female; reported coitus twice weekly with orgasms for both partners	Small, curved penis “did not trouble the patient before he got married” (p. 332), and he only sought help because he could not ejaculate inside the vagina and he wanted to have children
XY intersex, raised as female (1)	At puberty became typically male and chose to change sex	Not clearly stated	Case report	“He was totally relieved by being told he was a male” (p. 1,151)	At age 22 married as a man
Incomplete AIS; 46 XY; raised as female with enlarged clitoris (1)	At age 33 had breasts removed	Breast removal in adulthood	Case report; hormonal, anatomical, and psychiatric testing	Individual had strongly male gender identity apparently from a very early age; sexual orientation to females	Male gender identity evident in early childhood

Appendix B

	Mating	Social affiliation	Pair bond formation	Partner preference	Mate guarding	Pair bond maintenance
Prairie vole (<i>Microtus ochrogaster</i>)	<p>↑ c-Fos^a: mPFC, NAcc, AON, BLA, PVN, VP, BNST, mPOA, mPFC-NAcc, mPFC-NAcc, mPFC-NAcc, BNST, mPFC-SHy</p> <p>↑ DA^c: NAcc</p> <p>↑ AVPr^d: VP</p>	<p>↑ c-Fos^{b+,n}: VTA, LS, MeA, VP, BNST, AH, mPOA, ventrolateral VMH, PeV</p> <p>↑ eFC^b: mPFC-NAcc</p> <p>↑ rsFC^d: ACC-NAcc-BLA-RSC-VTA-LS-MeA-VP, RSC-PVN, BLA-DG</p> <p>↑ AVPr^r: VP</p>	<p>↑ rsFC^d: VP-LS-RSC, ACC-vHC</p> <p>↑ D2R^e: NAcc</p> <p>↑ OpR^k: NAcc</p> <p>↑ AVPr^q: LS</p> <p>↓ rsFC^d: LS-dHC</p>	<p>↑ rsFC^d: LS-VP</p> <p>↑ DA^c: NAcc</p> <p>↑ OpR^k: NAcc</p> <p>↑ OTR^o: NAcc</p> <p>↑ AVPr^r: VP</p> <p>↓ rsFC^d: BLA-NAcc, LS-RSC</p> <p>↓ AVPr^p: RSC</p> <p>↓ ERα^m: MeA</p>	<p>↑ c-Fosⁿ: LS, VP, VTA, BNST, mPOA, VMN, AH</p> <p>↑ D1R^e: NAcc</p> <p>↓ rsFC^d: BLA-NAcc-VTA, ACC-LS</p>	<p>↑ rsFC^d: LS-mPFC-dHC, VP-VTA</p> <p>↑ D1R^{e,c+}: NAcc</p> <p>↑ CB1^{a+}: NAcc</p> <p>↓ rsFC^d: BLA-NAcc-VTA, ACC-LS</p>
Mandarin vole (<i>Microtus mandarinus</i>)	<p>↓ AR, T^{g+}:LS, MeA, mPOA, VMH</p>	<p>↑ DA^{f+}: NAcc</p>	<p>↓ D2R^{e+}: NAcc</p>	<p>↑ OT^{d+}</p> <p>↑ c-Fos^{d+}: BNST, LS, mPOA, PVN, SON, MD, VMH, MeA, CeA</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>NA</p>
Titi monkey (<i>Callicebinae</i> spp.)	<p>NA</p>	<p>↑ FDG^h: NAcc, LS, ACC, CeA, HC, PVN, SON</p> <p>↑ OT^sCPSTABLEENTER↓</p> <p>OTR^z: HC</p> <p>↓ OpR^v</p>	<p>↑ FDG^f: NAcc, VP, mPOA, MeA, SON, LS</p> <p>↑ D1Rⁱ: LS</p>	<p>↑ AVP^x</p>	<p>↑ FDGⁱ: right LS, left PCC, left ACC</p> <p>↓ FDGⁱ: MeA</p> <p>↑ D1R^u</p>	<p>↑ FDG^e: NAcc, VP</p> <p>↑ D1Rⁱ: LS</p>
Common marmoset (<i>Callithrix</i> spp.)	<p>NA</p>	<p>↑ OT^t</p> <p>↓ D2R^w</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>↑ OT^t</p>	<p>↓ OT^y</p>	<p>NA</p>

Table 3. Species comparison wrt brain regions and connectomes involved in mating and monogamous behaviors.

+, increase of; -, decrease of; NA, data not found by the time of this review.

AR, androgen receptor expression (male voles). AVP, arginine-vasopressin concentration level (exogenous and endogenous). AVPR, arginine-vasopressin receptor binding. c-Fos, c-fos protein expression (immunohistological detection correlates). D1R, dopamine D1 receptor binding. D2R, dopamine D2 receptor binding. DA, extracellular dopamine concentration (microdialysis detection). Efc, electrophysiological functional connectivity (low-frequency signal coherence correlates). ERα, estrogen receptor alpha binding. FDG, [¹⁸F]-fluorodeoxyglucose uptake (metabolic activity correlates). OpR, opioid receptor binding. OT, oxytocin concentration level (exogenous and endogenous). OTR, oxytocin receptor binding. rsFC, resting-state functional connectivity (low-frequency fMRI BOLD-signal correlates). T, testosterone expression (male voles, immunohistological).

ACC, anterior cingulate cortex. BLA, basolateral amygdala. BNST, bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. CeA, central amygdala. DG, dentate gyrus. HC, hippocampus. dHC, dorsal hippocampus. MeA, medial amygdala. MOB, main olfactory bulb. LS, lateral septum. mPFC, medial prefrontal cortex. mPOA, medial preoptic area. NAcc, nucleus accumbens. PCC, posterior cingulate cortex. PeV, periventricular nucleus of the thalamus. PVN, paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus. RSC, retrosplenial cortex; SON, supraoptic nucleus. SHy, septohypothalamic nucleus. vHC, ventral hippocampus. VMN, ventromedial nucleus of the hypothalamus. VP, ventral pallidum. VTA, ventral tegmental area.